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Video-based AAL and intimate pictures – criminal liability in European, Irish, and Polish law

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Abstract. Active and Assisted Living (AAL) technologies offer solutions for addressing healthcare challenges associated with ageing societies and a shortage of care personnel. At the same time, these technologies raise significant privacy issues, which may constitute a barrier to the sustainable adoption and acceptance of AAL. In particular, concerns arise from the presence of cameras in intimate situations, including nudity, and the potential production and dissemination of intimate pictures, which constitutes a risk for AAL users. The paper compares the regimes of criminal liability for making and disseminating intimate pictures under EU, Irish, and Polish law. The study aims to help AAL users understand their legal protection, and give providers and developers more insight into their legal responsibilities. The paper first presents different understandings of an intimate picture in each jurisdiction, followed by a discussion of what the crime entails and who may be liable for it. The conclusion includes a checklist of rules concerning criminal liability, which may be useful for AAL users and providers, and conclusions *de lege ferenda*.

Keywords. Active and Assisted Living, intimate pictures, criminal law.

1. Introduction

Active and Assisted Living (AAL) technologies have emerged as a promising solution to the healthcare challenges faced by ageing societies and a shortage of care personnel [1]. These technologies aim to provide support and assistance to elderly individuals in their daily lives, with the ultimate goal of enabling them to live independently and comfortably in their own homes. Among the various technological components used in AAL, visual components such as video or depth cameras are particularly promising as they provide a natural and direct way to record situations and movements and supply rich information – for example, about accidents like falls [2]. However, the use of cameras in private spaces raises significant privacy concerns that may hinder the sustainable adoption and acceptance of AAL [3, 4]. One of the biggest concerns is the presence of cameras in intimate situations, including nudity, which may lead to a potential production and dissemination of intimate pictures and constitute a risk for AAL users [3, 5, 6]. These issues are being addressed not only from a technical perspective [7, 8], but also by the law.

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This contribution aims to compare the regimes of criminal liability for the production and dissemination of intimate pictures under EU, Irish, and Polish law, and to identify potential gaps and shortcomings in the existing legal regimes. The study provides a comprehensive overview of the legal protections available to users of AAL systems, and offers insights into the legal responsibilities of providers and developers in these jurisdictions. Firstly, the concept of an intimate picture is examined in each jurisdiction. Secondly, the paper analyses the elements of a crime in the respective legislations. Thirdly, the potential criminal liability of natural and legal persons, including AAL providers, is investigated. This paper focuses on Ireland and Poland with the aim of analysing countries with different legal traditions (common law and civil law) and distinct socio-economic contexts. The two countries' EU member status also provokes questions concerning the level of legal harmonisation, and coherence with the Union's law.

2. Understanding of an intimate picture

The first step in investigating criminal liability in the context of intimate pictures is to identify the material scope of the research, i.e. what legal acts regulate that issue and how an intimate image may be defined. Currently, there is no EU legislation concerning intimate pictures. However, in March 2022, the European Commission proposed a new Directive on combating violence against women and domestic violence (Directive) [9], which includes measures on the “non-consensual distribution of intimate and manipulated” images (Article 7). In Ireland, the Harassment, Harmful Communications and Related Offences Act 2020 (Act) was passed [10]. The Act contains two offences related to intimate pictures: recording or distributing (section 3), and distributing, publishing, or threatening to do so (section 2). In Polish law, unconsented depicting or disseminating a “representation of a naked person” or “a person engaged in sexual activity” constitute a criminal offence under Article 191a §1 of the Penal Code (Polish: Kodeks Karny, KK) since 2010 [11]. This paper discusses the notion of intimate pictures in the identified regulations in chronological order, i.e., from the Polish one, through the Irish Act, to the proposed Directive, which allows tracking changes in the legislative approach to intimate pictures.

The location of Article 191a §1 KK is not without relevance for its interpretation. That article is located in the part of the Code concerning offences against freedom, and the value protected by Article 191a §1 KK is a person's freedom of deciding upon depicting and disseminating one's representation [12]. Polish law does not employ the term “intimate pictures” but instead uses the phrase “representation of a naked person or a person engaged in sexual activity”. However, these two situations may be considered jointly as intimate ones. The sexual activity shall be interpreted broadly, taking into account cultural and social context [13, 14]. Nudity is not legally defined in Poland. In a case like that, the literal interpretation, based on dictionaries and common understanding, should be pursued, following the principles of strict interpretation and *in dubio pro reo* (“[when] in doubt, rule for the accused”) (Article 1§1 KK, Article 5§2 Code of Criminal Proceedings) [11, 15, 16, 17]. Consequently, a naked person would mean a person not wearing any piece of clothing or being covered. That interpretation is considered by many scholars as irrational and against *ratio legis* [18]. Instead, some propose considering a person naked when “a considerable part” of the body is uncovered” [19, 20], or when some particular parts of the body are revealed, i.e., genitals and, in the case

of a female, her breasts [21, 22]. To reconcile various approaches and limit legal uncertainty, Filek [16] proposes defining a naked person as a person whose at least one intimate part of the body is recognizable. That definition, not contested in the discourse, may be seen as a consensual one [23].

In Irish law, the term “intimate picture” is legally defined in section 1 of the Act. Under that section, intimate image “means any visual representation made by any means, including any photographic, film, video or digital representation.” The law defines also the content of the intimate image, providing a closed list of representations:

- a) “of what is, or purports to be the person’s genitals, buttocks or anal region and, in the case of a female, her breasts;
- b) of the underwear covering the person’s genitals, buttocks or anal region and, in the case of a female, her breasts;
- c) in which the person is nude, or
- d) in which the person is engaged in sexual activity.”

The definition of an intimate image provided in Irish law has several significant implications. Firstly, it distinguishes four types of intimate images. This differentiation suggests that these conditions are viewed as distinct by the law, even though they can occur simultaneously. Secondly, while nudity is listed as one constitutive criterion of an intimate picture, it is not defined by the law. The fact that the law distinguishes between images of intimate areas or underwear covering them and images of nude persons may imply that being lightly covered does not constitute nudity. However, this distinction may not be rational as a person can be nude, but their intimate parts may be covered. In such a scenario, the image would be protected under section 1 (c). This interpretation is supported by Bowie [24], who notes that the Act was intended to prevent situations like the tragic case of a person detained in 2017 after walking naked on a Dublin’s street and whose arrest was recorded by CCTV cameras, and who subsequently took her own life. Thirdly, it is worth noticing that the Irish definition covers also “what purports to be” a person’s intimate parts, a definition that encompasses Photoshopped images and deepfakes [24, 25, 26].

The proposed EU Directive aims to “effectively combat violence against women and domestic violence throughout the EU” by laying down minimum rules on the definition of relevant criminal offences, including “non-consensual sharing of intimate or manipulated material” (Article 7). Despite its name, the Directive understands the victim as “any person, regardless of sex or gender” (Article 4(c)). The Directive makes a distinction between intimate and manipulated images, videos, and “other material.” According to Article 7(b), manipulation refers to “making it appear as though another person is engaged in sexual activities.” Consequently, the provisions governing manipulated material would not extend to a deepfake that depicts a person naked. Article 7(a) pertains to the dissemination of “intimate images, or videos or other material depicting sexual activities, of another person” through ICTs. However, the extent of this norm is ambiguous, and it may only apply to representations of sexual activities. Rigotti and McGlynn [27] suggest a broader interpretation that includes “images which are deemed sexual and/or intimate”. The absence of a clear definition of an intimate image is a notable drawback of the Directive. It would be advantageous to establish a comprehensive description of what constitutes an intimate image, drawing on the legal frameworks of Member States and academic research.

3. Matter of a crime

To comprehensively explore the criminal liability surrounding intimate pictures, it is essential to examine the elements that constitute a crime. Across the three jurisdictions discussed, the common condition of a crime is the absence of consent from the depicted person. There are no specific requirements regarding the form in which consent must be given, which can lead to various difficulties in cases of dispute. In the context of AAL, providers can potentially mitigate the illegality of intimate pictures by obtaining the user's acceptance that such pictures may be taken in specific situations, such as assisting in toileting.

In the investigated jurisdictions two actions constitute a crime: production and dissemination of intimate pictures (Article 191a §1 KK, Section 2 and 3 Act, Article 7(a) and 7(b) Directive). Committing either of these actions separately is sufficient to constitute a crime. Consequently, disseminating legally obtained nude images is sufficient to commit a crime. It is important to note that consent for dissemination may be restricted [20, 28, 29]. For example, an individual using AAL technologies may agree to allow their images to be viewed only by AAL provider's employees, care facility staff, or family members. Disseminating such images to anyone beyond this group would constitute a criminal offence.

The third element that may be required for an action to be illegal is harm. In Irish law, section 3 of the Act requires harm to occur as an element of the crime, while section 2 requires the offence to be committed "with intent to cause harm or being reckless as to whether harm is caused." Both sections define harm as "serious interference with that other person's peace and privacy, causing alarm, distress or harm to that other person," including psychological harm (section 1). As noticed by Bowie [24], these provisions "could potentially limit prosecutorial possibilities, especially in relation to the intent of the perpetrator." The law mandates that the harm and its connection with the action or intention of the perpetrator be proven beyond a reasonable doubt. There are two potential challenges resulting from this requirement, as identified by McGlynn and Rackley [25]. Firstly, there is a risk that these provisions "reify an 'ideal victim' by predetermining what is seen to be the 'appropriate' response from victims." This may result in a situation where prosecution is unlikely if the victim does not react as expected. Secondly, if there are multiple victims or a potential victim is unaware that they have been victimized, prosecution may not be feasible. However, from the perspective of an AAL provider, the requirement of harm excludes criminality of an action if the provider acts diligently and with good intentions. Contrary to Irish regulations, there is no reference to harm in the proposed Directive or the Polish law. Because Article 191a §1 KK safeguards personal freedom, and non-consensual depiction of a person in an intimate situation is considered implicitly harmful [12, 19].

Reference to harm brings the discussion to the fourth element of a crime, which is the purposefulness of an action. Section 2(1) Act conditions the criminal nature of the act on the intention of the perpetrator to cause harm or their recklessness as to whether harm is caused, to the extent predictable to a "reasonable person" (Section 2(2)). Similarly, Polish law defines intent as a will to commit a prohibited act or "foreseeing the possibility of perpetrating it, and accepting it" (Article 9 §1 KK). Additionally, a crime may be committed by omission if a person who had borne a legal, special duty to prevent such a consequence, failed to do so (Article 2 KK). Arguably, this provision can be applied to providers of AAL systems. On one hand, the main function of AAL technology is to support the quality of life and independence of users. On the other hand,

the protection of privacy, including intimate situations, is a crucial requirement of users [5]. Moreover, as AAL providers deliver care and assistance products, they are in a relation of trust with users. For these reasons, there is a high probability that they have a special duty of care. Consequently, providers may commit the crime by omission in Polish law. However, there is a lack of relevant case law to verify that hypothesis.

Finally, it is important to note that Polish legislation incorporates provisions that address the methods employed to make an intimate picture. According to Article 191a §1 KK, the act of capturing an intimate image is deemed unlawful only if it involves deception, coercion, or threat against the victim. Therefore, using a hidden camera would constitute a criminal offence, whereas capturing the same image with a visible camera would be permissible. In the context of video-based AAL a potential act of deception may occur if the camera is operational, but the user has reasonable grounds to believe otherwise (for instance, if the control device incorrectly indicates that the system is turned off). However, it should be emphasized that the offence is only committed if such deception is intentional or results from negligence.

To conclude, in all discussed jurisdictions, an intended production or dissemination of an intimate image without the consent of the depicted person is a prohibited act. In Ireland harm is an additional condition for an act to be considered criminal. Under Polish law, the crime in question may be committed also by omission, on the basis of AAL providers' duty of care. Moreover, in Polish jurisdiction capturing an intimate image is deemed unlawful only if it involves deception, coercion, or threat against the victim.

4. Criminal liability of natural and legal persons

In the context of producing and disseminating intimate images, the question arises as to who may be held accountable for the offence. The crucial point is whether only individuals (such as employees or managers of the AAL provider) or legal entities, (the AAL provider as a company) may be subject to prosecution. Notably, the proposed EU Directive does not include specific provisions regarding the criminal liability of legal entities. It does not preclude criminal liability of organisations or companies but rather leaves those issues to Member States' laws.

Both Irish and Polish laws contain provisions about the criminal liability of people other than just the direct perpetrators. Section 6(1) Act states that in some circumstances the managers of a company are liable for acts of the body corporate. To apply that provision, an offence must be committed by a body corporate, and it must be proven that the offence can be attributed to "any wilful neglect" or was committed with the consent or connivance of a manager. In the context of section 6(1) Act, "managers" refers to the directors, managers, secretaries, or other officers of the body corporate or of a person purporting to act in such a capacity. Similarly, in Polish law every person that was both in a position to and legally obliged to prevent the crime but did not do so is criminally liable as an associate (Article 18 §3 KK). Additionally, whenever a special duty of care exists, a person may be held liable on the ground of negligence (Article 2 KK). In the context of a company providing AAL, these rules may be applied to managers on various levels of management, but also to employees working on the development of technology.

Additionally, in some cases legal persons may also be held criminally liable. According to Section 6(1) Act, if the conditions discussed in the relations to managers are satisfied, the corporate body itself is guilty of an offence and subject to prosecution and punishment. Thus, the AAL provider as a company, not just its employees, may be

held criminally liable. Similarly, Polish law allows for the criminal prosecution of a legal person if three requirements are met. The first condition requires the identification and conviction of the natural person who committed the prohibited act under Article 4 of the Act of 28 October 2002 on the Liability of Collective Entities for Prohibited Acts [30]. The second condition is that the convicted natural person acted in the name or interest of the legal entity, and the act itself must have potentially benefited the legal person in any way under Article 3. Finally, the legal entity must have failed to exercise due diligence in selecting or supervising employees or other agents who committed the prohibited act, under Article 5. All three conditions must be met simultaneously for a natural person to be criminally liable. This high bar for criminal liability means that, in most cases, the AAL provider would not be criminally liable under Polish law. Conversely, Irish regulations make it easier to hold the company responsible for the crime of producing or disseminating intimate images.

5. Conclusions

Two kinds of conclusions can be drawn from the current paper. First, rules concerning criminal liability in Ireland and Poland may be presented in the form of a checklist with questions. This checklist may be useful both for AAL users and providers for getting informed about their rights and obligations. The Directive is not included in that summary due to a lack of detailed norms.

Table 1. Checklist of conditions of criminal liability in the context of intimate pictures in Ireland and Poland.

Ireland	Poland
1. Is a picture an intimate one?	
1.1. Does it depict a person engaged in sexual activity?	1.1. Is depicted person identifiable?
1.2. Is it a picture a) of what is, or purports to be, the person's genitals, buttocks or anal region and, in the case of a female, her breasts; b) of the underwear covering the person's genitals, buttocks or anal region and, in the case of a female, her breasts; c) in which the person is nude, or d) in which the person is engaged in sexual activity?	1.2. Does it depict a person engaged in sexual activity? 1.3. Is at least one intimate part of the body recognisable?
If the answer to 1.1. or 1.2. a, b, c, or d is "yes", then a picture is an intimate one.	If the answers to 1.1. and to 1.2. or 1.3. are "yes", the picture is an intimate one.
2. Was there a criminal offence?	
2.1. Did you depict an intimate picture?	2.1. Did you depict an intimate picture?
2.2. Did you disseminate an intimate picture?	2.2. Did you disseminate an intimate picture?
2.3. Did you do that without the consent of the depicted person?	2.3. Did you do that without the consent of the depicted person?
2.4. Did your action cause or intended to cause harm?	2.4. Did you do that intentionally? 2.5. Did you make an intimate picture using deception, coercion, or threat? 2.6. Did you have a special duty of care and failed to comply with it?
If the answers to 2.1. or 2.2., and both 2.3. and 2.4. are "yes", the prohibited act has been committed.	If the answers to 2.1. and 2.3. and 2.4., and 2.5., or to 2.2. and 2.3. and 2.4. or 2.6. are "yes", the prohibited act has been committed.
3. Criminal liability of manager or organisation	

3.1. Did the prohibited action result from the operation of the body corporate?	3.1. Did a person have a special obligation to prevent the crime?
3.2. Was the offence committed with the consent or connivance of a manager, or can it be attributed to any wilful neglect?	3.2. Did a person have a special duty of care?
If the answers to 3.1. and 3.2. are “yes”, the managers can be criminally liable.	If the answer to 3.1. or 3.2. is “yes”, the managers can be criminally liable.
	3.3. Was the offender of the crime convicted?
	3.4. Did the offender act in the name or the interest of an organisation?
	3.5. Did the legal entity fail to exercise due diligence in selecting or supervising employees or agents that committed a crime?
If the answers to 3.1. and 3.2. are “yes”, the company may be criminally liable.	If the answers to 3.3., 3.4., and 3.5. are “yes”, the organisation may be criminally liable.

Second, a critical comparison of three legal systems yields important insights for potential legal reforms. Firstly, Irish law stands out for its comprehensive and precise definition of an intimate picture, encompassing various types and enhancing legal certainty. This could serve as a valuable reference point for other legislations. Secondly, the requirement of proven harm in Irish law may inadvertently limit the protection afforded to individuals. To better safeguard individuals’ rights, it is crucial to recognise the inherent harm of unconsented intimate pictures, as in the Polish approach. Thirdly, there is a pressing need to clarify and harmonize rules on the criminal liability of legal entities within the EU. The significant disparities observed among the examined Member States necessitate a cohesive and uniform approach. These three conclusions should guide EU legislators in future efforts to refine the Directive, ensuring harmonization that benefits both users and providers of AAL technologies by clearly defining their respective responsibilities and rights.

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